

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for three cytoplasmic male sterile lines

J. S. Bijral, T. R. Sharma, B. Singh, B. B. Gupta, and K. S. Kanwal, SKUAST, Regional Agriculture Research Station, R.S. Pura 181102, India

We crossed 35 short-, medium-, and long-duration indica cultivars with cytoplasmic male sterile lines Zhen Shan 97 A, IR48483 A, and IR46830 A to identify maintainers and restorers. The F₁ hybrids were grown in the field.

The main panicles of five randomly selected plants of each cross were harvested and spikelet fertility calculated. Cultivars showing more than 75% spikelet fertility were classified as effective restorers, those between 1 and 75% fertility as partial restorers, and those of less than 1%, maintainers (see table).

IR31802-48-2-2-2 and RR8585 restored fertility of all three CMS lines; China 988, China 1007, and Sattari maintained their sterility. Recurrent backcrosses with China 988 and China 1007 are underway, to transfer cytoplasmic male sterility into their nuclear background. □

Restorers and maintainers for Zhen Shan 97 A, IR48483 A, and IR46830 A CMS lines at Regional Agriculture Research Station, R. S. Pura, India.^a

Variety	Zhen Shan 97 A	IR48483 A	IR46830 A
IR8	–	–	PR
IR36	–	R	R
IR42	–	M	M
IR50	–	R	PR
IR21820-154-3-2-2	–	R	M
IR28150-84-3-3-2	–	R	–
IR28228-12-3-1-1-2	–	M	PR
IR31802-48-2-2-2	R	R	R
IR31851-63-1-2-3-2	R	R	–
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	R	R	PR
IR32429-47-3-2-2	–	R	R
CR666-1	PR	R	R
CR666-7	R	PR	PR
CR666-49	M	M	–
CR666-36-4	M	M	M
Sattari	M	M	M
China 988	M	M	M
China 1007	M	M	M
RR8585	R	R	R
VL 15	R	R	PR
PC-19	–	R	–
Jaya	–	–	R
Sadri	PR	PR	–
IET1410	R	–	–
Musatareme	R	–	–
Mehr	PR	–	–
Domsiah	PR	–	–
Ranbir Basmati	–	–	R
Rasi	–	R	PR
Dular	–	R	–
ITA173	–	M	–
ITA183	–	PR	PR
B3016 B	–	M	M
Khuch	–	M	M
K85-2	–	–	M

^aR = restorer (75% spikelet fertility), PR = partial restorer (1-75% spikelet fertility), M = maintainer (1% spikelet fertility), – = damaged seedlings.

Androgenesis in rice treated with physical and chemical mutagens

P. Boyadjiev, Pham Coung, M. Naidenova, D. Pouleva, and K. Perfanov, Institute of Introduction and Plant Genetic Resources, K. Malkov, Sadovo, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

We studied the effect of mutagens on androgenesis, using L₄₄, a dihaploid line obtained through anther culture of the F₁ hybrid Bellozem/ Plovdiv 22. Mutagenic treatments were 1) gamma rays ⁶⁰Co at 25 kR, 2) 0.004 M sodium azide (NaN₃), and 3) 25 kR + 0.003 M NaN₃. The NaN₃ treatment involved soaking seeds in the mutagenic solution for 18 h, then sowing them with a control for panicle collection. Callus induction and plant regeneration were

Table 1. Germination and efficiency of callus induction in anther culture of rice treated with mutagens.

Treatment	Germination rate (%)	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Callus induction ^a	
			no.	%
Control	44.8	1000	364	36.4
25 kR treatment	31.6	995	134	13.5
0.004 M NaN ₃	16.8	939	169	18.0
25 kR + 0.003 M NaN ₃	20.4	983	47	4.8

^a $\frac{\text{Calli induced (no.)}}{\text{Anthers inoculated (no.)}} \times 100$.

Table 2. Plant regeneration in anther culture of rice treated with mutagens.

Treatment	Calli inoculated (no.)	Non differentiated calli		Calli showing rhizogenesis		Green plants (no.)	
		no.	%	no.	%	Total	Av
Control	397	62	15.6	178	44.8	246	0.62
25 kR	119	56	47.1	33	27.7	42	0.3
0.004 M NaN ₃	88	38	43.2	28	31.8	59	0.67
25 kR + 0.003 M NaN ₃	54	23	42.6	13	24.1	41	0.76